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Youth Empowerment Through Technical Vocational Education And Training (TVET) For Economic Growth In The Era Of Uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) plays a vital role all over the world in addressing youth unemployment, poverty and skill development. It is an integral part of national development strategies in many societies because of its impact on human resources development, productivity and economic growth. In this era of uncertainty in Nigeria where the youths who are the major population workforce are faced with series of challenges hindering economic growth, there is need therefore to examine how youths could be empowered through TVET for economic growth. In the light of this, the study discussed youth empowerment, youth empowerment programmes in Nigeria, need for youth empowerment in the era of economic uncertainty and strategies for empowering youths through TVET. It was recommended among others that TVET experts should update curriculum to meet the requirements of the labour market, policy makers should formulate and ensure implementation of policies that will benefit all forms of TVET.

Keywords: Youth Empowerment, Uncertainty, Technical and vocational education and Training (TVET)

INTRODUCTION

Youths are one of the greatest assets that any nation can have. Not only are they legitimately regarded as the future leaders, they are potentially the greatest investment for a country's growth and development. Good number of the Nigeria population falls under the youth age bracket. This group age possess great potentials and are very active and eager to expend their packaged energy. This implies that they will expend their talents in any available opportunity, positive or negative, depending on the opportunity most easily accessible. Ahmed in Ibeneme and Okorafor (2013) stated that considering their strength, creativity, potentials and their tendencies not only will they outlive today's leaders they will outshine them and will be great asset to any nation if their energies and creativity are tapped and utilised. In line with this view, Achuma, Obiah, Anyanor Anikam, Ahumible and Dimkpa (2015) opined that the extent of youth's vitality, responsible conduct and roles in the society is correlated with the development of their country. Through their creative talents and labour power, a nation makes giant strides in economic growth and development. On the other hand, considering their population, strength and exuberance they could poses great threat to a nation if their empowerment is neglected. The author further stated that youths can also constitute a threat to national stability and even survival if left to drift, remain unemployed and misguided.

One of the ways of harnessing potentials of youths in Nigeria is through education and training. Providing young people with quality education and training in relevant fields will equip them with the knowledge

and skills needed to succeed in the modern economy. It is important to note that it is only quality TVET will provide the much needed youth empowerment.

Empowerment is referred to as opportunities being given to a group of youth to be able to control their own life or situation they find themselves. (Achana, Obiah, Anyangor, Anukam, Ahumible and Dimkpa, 2015). It involves equipping the youths with the potentials by teaching them relevant skills, knowledge and competencies that will enable them function effectively after graduation. When youths are skilled they will be useful to themselves and the society they belong and this will extend to the larger society. TVET is the process of preparing individuals for occupational fields and effective participation in the world of work. It is the essential part of development for any nation to grow economically (Abdullah in Elana, Chiorlu and Leka (2021). Investing in TVET will enable the young people to create their own opportunities and contribute to economic growth.

Nigeria- like many developing countries is faced with uncertainties arising from various sources as economic downturn, political instability, insecurity, pandemic among others, that have resulted to a high level of unemployment, poverty and underdevelopment. In such a challenging economic environment it is imperative for the country to empower its youths through TVET to drive economic growth and development bearing in mind that the youth make up the productive population of a nation.

Youth Empowerment

Youth empowerment is perceived differently by different people. In Nigeria, youth empowerment is wrongly perceived by parents, government and youths. To parents, it is perceived as the sole responsibility of the government, the government sees youth empowerment as an avenue to initiate policies and programmes which although makes little impact on the lives of youths but soon hijacked by corrupt government officials for self-aggrandizement while the youths themselves neglect self-development and empowerment wholly depending on white-collar jobs (Ahmed in Ibeneme and Okorafor, 2013).

Youth empowerment is the attitudinal, structural and cultural process whereby young people gain the ability, authority and agency to make decisions and implement change in their own lives and the lives of other people including youths and adults. (Achuma, Madubike, Anyanjor, Ahumible and Dimkpa, 2015). It is the development of youth's ability to know about their rights, taking decisions that will benefit them plan their lives to avoid oppression, frustration or acceptance of suffering. In other words, youths are empowered when they acknowledge that they have and can create choices in life, are aware of implications of these choices, make informed decisions, freely take action based on their decisions and accept responsibility for the consequences of that action. In this study, youth empowerment is the process of enabling young people develop their skills and abilities, take control of their lives, participate in economic, social and political activities and contribute to their communities and society.

Youth Empowerment Programmes in Nigeria

Unemployment has become a major problem bedeviling the lives of Nigerian youths causing frustrations, dejections and dependence on family members and high rate of unemployment among youths in Nigeria which has contributed to the high rate of poverty and insecurity in the country. (National Bureau of statistics,2013). No country with a view to any form of future prosperity would allow its youths to wastage. Several measures has been put in place by government and non- governmental organizations (NGO) to empower the youths in order to minimise or scale down unemployment among them. Ekere in Ndukwe (2016) identified the various forms of youth empowerment for young people in various fields of specialisation as well as their communities as a whole to include, entrepreneurship training programme, advanced technology development, financial youth empowerment programme, skill acquisition and academic empowerment programme. The author further highlighted examples of empowerment schemes to include the following among others.

National Directorate of Employment: (NDE) This was the brainchild of the military government of Ibrahim Babangida in 1983. The scheme trains unemployed youths in skills and at the end of graduation empower them to start their own businesses.

National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP): The scheme was introduced by Olusegun Obasanjo. It empowered indigent unemployed people with fund to engage in economic activities especially agriculture.

Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P). Following the petroleum products subsidy an unemployment package SURE-P was launched by former president Good luck Jonathan in 2012. The scheme facilitated the employment of unemployed persons in various sectors such as health, education, agriculture as well as promotion of skill acquisition among youths.

N-POWER Scheme: The N- power Scheme was established under the administration of President Muhammed Buhari in 2015 to address unemployment in the country. It is for Nigeria between the ages of 18-35 years. According to Ndukwe (2010) unemployed youths are employed to work as teachers in schools, tax collectors, health assistant as well as farmers. N- Power has six categories which include; N-Teach, N-Health, N- Agro, N-Build, N-Creative and N- Tech. The N- Teach and N- Health are available for graduates who must have completed the mandatory one year National youth service scheme while N- Agro, N- Build ,N- Creative and N- Tech provides structure for the acquisition of skills as well as personal and career development thereby enabling the youth to work and earn monthly stipends.

Youth Empowerment Innovation in Nigeria (You WIN). This programme was established under President Goodluck Jonathan administration with the primary objective of generating jobs by encouraging and supporting aspiring youth entrepreneur in Nigeria to develop and execute business ideas that will lead to jobs creation. The programme provides aspiring youth with a platform to showcase their business acumen, skills and aspirations to investors and mentors in Nigeria (Udukeke and Usoro, 2023).

Youth Entrepreneurship Support Programme (YES-P). The youth Entrepreneurship Support Programme is a bank of industry's effort to address youth unemployment in Nigeria by building capacity of the youths and funding their business ideas. In other words, it's trains and awards loans to youths to startup small and medium enterprises. The federal government also funds the programme by offering youth entrepreneurs with interest free loans.

Tony Elumelu Foundation Entrepreneurship Programme (TEF): TEF is a privately owned empowerment programme founded by Tony Elumelu. The empowerment scheme was aimed at motivating young African with innovation business ideas by offering them grants to bring those ideas into reality.

With all these initiatives among others much has not been achieved in reducing youths unemployment in Nigeria due to poor implementation, lack of enabling environment, tribalism , nepotism among others Adebayo (2018) stated that the effectiveness of youth empowerment initiatives in Nigeria has been hindered by factors such as corruption, mismanagement, poor planning policy, inconsistency and poor governance.

Need for Empowering youths through TVET in the era of economic uncertainty

Nigeria has experience sessions of economic uncertainty which has resulted to recession due to political instability, sudden central bank intervention, petroleum products price increase, pandemic among others. Economic uncertainty refers to as loss of predictability or stability in the economy making it difficult for businesses and individuals to make informed financial decisions. This could be caused by factors such as political instability, fluctuations in the stock market, changes in government policies, global economic changes etc. Tunjo (2022) stated that the country's economic outlook remains uncertain and threatened by many issues arising from political instability, pandemics, natural disaster, technological disruption, persistent inflationary pressures and arising brain drain. Corroborating with this view Ihugba, Odii and Njoku (2013) opined that there is a growing uncertainty in the international market as a result of high oil prices in the he global market which has led to energy and food crisis, appreciation in the dollar against global currencies, halt in foreign investment flow. These disruption make it difficult for businesses to operate and hindered economic growth. It is worth noting that no reasonable or rational investor would

wish to invest in a country marked by instability, confusion, and uncertainty. Ozili (2022) asserted that instability and uncertainty are important factors responsible for African poor investment records over the last two decades.

The instability experiences in Nigeria over time cannot be dissociated from the country's massive dependence on crude oil, which remains the largest source of fiscal revenues and export earnings. Ayerin and Fanibuyan (2022) reported that Nigerian's economy is a developing country that earns over 90% of its revenue from crude oil export and most of the recent economic shock have been linked to crude oil prices in the past. The author further stated that the economy is exposed to external uncertainty from crude oil exports which trigger domestic uncertainty leading to macroeconomic instability in Nigeria.

Moreso, Nigeria depends on major exporting country in Asia and North America for essential imported consumer goods. A major increase in the price of imports by China and India can have real effects on the Nigeria economy. Similarly, Nigeria's economy is interconnected to the economy of its neighbouring West African countries such as Togo, Benin and Niger. These West African countries depends heavily on Nigeria for trade supplies such as electricity supply. A sharp increase in electricity tariffs in Nigeria can transmit shocks to these countries, thereby creating spillover through unexpected changes in trade tariffs for electricity.

In this era of economic uncertainty in Nigeria which is orchestrated by inflation, political instability, ethnic crisis, poverty insecurity and unemployment among others, there is need to equip youths with the knowledge and skills for the future so as to contribute to nations economic growth and development. The youth's choice for contribution in nation's economic, social and cultural development is maximised through the process of empowerment (Ahmed in Ibeneme and Okorafor , 2013) Empowering the youths will not only checkmate hunger, poverty and unemployment that threatens economic growth but also reduces drastically the number of youths that participate in social vices as well as increase their awareness for sustainability factors.

Reducing unemployment among youths is a major concern for TVET in Nigeria. It provides the skills and competence required in the world of work. TVET calls for training and development of competent youths who are equipped with the various skills needed by the labour market. Abokede (2012) stated that TVET have been adjudged the catalyst for employment and prime agent of empowerment. In line with by this view, Ajigo and Azu- Nandi (2015) stated that the key aspect of youth empowerment is enabling the youths to gain useful skills with which they could be gainfully self- employed. It is therefore imperative that Nigerian youths be empowered through TVET programme to acquire skills that will enable them to create wealth, reduce poverty and ensure optimum development in the era of economic uncertainty.

Strategies for Youth Empowerment through TVET

The key to economic growth is creation of employment to all. The youth of any nation makes up a greater percentage of its population and accounts for the workforce. When the greater percentage of the nation's population are unemployed it means that there is wastage of the productive workforce, low national income per capital, overdependence on government, general poverty, poor industrial production and lack of self- reliance by the youth leading to poor national development (Ozobu and Omale, 2013). Quality TVET is widely recognized as having an important role to play in tackling youth unemployment. TVET helps to accelerate economic growth, provide market labour supply, minimise unemployment and underemployment, impart technical knowledge and trim down poverty (Onele, Imeku and Nwose, 2017). Unfortunately, TVET system has not been given its rightful place in Nigeria. UNESCO in Akamobi (2022) confirmed this in a statement that inspite of the contribution that TVET can make in developing the formal and informal sectors of the economy not much has been done to address the challenges the programme. If TVET will be an effective youth empowerment strategy for attaining economic growth, then its status and attractiveness has to be enhanced through the following ways.

Implementation of appropriate policy for TVET: The entry of a new government create an opportunity for the new government to re-evaluates existing policies for the current economic realities in the country but most times policies (including TVET policy) change when new government assumes office without

determining the relevance of the policy to the system. Ihugba, Odii and Njoku (2013) stated that inconsistent government policies are the major challenge to entrepreneurship in Nigeria. If TVET will be an effective youth empowerment strategy for attaining economic growth then government desiring such must put in place viable and consistent policies and systems to support all forms of TVET (formal, informal, public or private).

Curriculum update: The quality of education and training given to youth depends greatly in the ability of institutions to adjust their education content to the changing skill requirements of the nation. TVET curriculum needs to be expanded and renewed to be relevant to the employer's needs. Okoli, Wejinya, Agam and Asugi in Akamobi (2022) opined that the current TVET curriculum is weak and not flexible enough to meet the technological changes and diverse needs of different clients thereby resulting to TVET graduates experiencing technological shock when they enter the job . Today automation and computerization has taken transition and production jobs such as clerical works, assembling-line work, troubleshooting and repairs require technology skills. As a consequence, vast majority of jobs are at high risks of automation.

Adopting appropriate pedagogical approaches: Not only the educational contents need to be renewed, how the content is delivered is crucial to determining its success in empowering the recipients. Innovative ways of delivering TVET programmes are needed in order to strengthen its effectiveness towards educating for empowerment .The pedagogical approaches should be such that will appeal to the students variously providing them with opportunities to discover ideas and facts in the real- world settings through their own efforts.

Procurement and maintenance of teaching facilities: Many graduates of TVET seems not to acquire the adequate skills to be employed or create jobs for themselves. This is associated with the inadequacy of material resources both in quality and quantity for a sound TVET programme. Empowering youths through skill acquisition requires that necessary facilities need to be supplied and maintained when the need arises for effective teaching to take place. Abbo and Akunola (2021) opined that teaching facilities are central to developing students' skills and competencies, motivation and knowledge.

Strengthening linkage between TVET institutions and industries: The major challenge militating TVET manpower development for economic growth and development is the linkage between the industries and TVET institutions. TVET institutions should have close linkage with the world of work to solicit support of industries in the provision of practical training through such activities as donation of equipment and tools, staff exchange programmes and placement of trainees on work experience. Collaboration with the industries will create opportunities for students to develop their skills and practical experience and as well make graduates of TVET ready to take up jobs in the industries.

UNESCO in Olubiyi (2022) highlighted strategies for empowering youths through TVET to include; provision of adequate funding, curriculum reformation, quality assurance, professional development of teachers, constant monitoring and effective evaluation, provision of workshop training and collaboration for capacity building, giving free taxation for enterprises that engage in TVET training expenses and apprenticeship for Nigerian youths.

CONCLUSION

The productive capacity of youths in terms of skills and competencies have been the key driver of empowerment. This means that skilled and competent manpower play a key role in the development processes. In the era of economic uncertainty in Nigeria which is orchestrated by inflation, political instability insecurity poverty, unemployment among others there is need for the youth to be empowered through TVET so as to equip them with necessary knowledge and skills needed to survive in today's environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To empower youth through TVET in the era of uncertainty, the paper recommended the following among others;

1. Experts in TVET programmes should make curriculum content more extensive and flexible to meet the requirements of the employers of labour.
2. Policy makers should formulate and ensure implementation of policies that will address the problems of TVET at all levels.
3. TVET administrators should organise seminars, workshops and conferences with the aim of enhancing the knowledge of TVET educators in their areas in order to be relevant in today's dynamic and globalised environment.
4. Funding of TVET programmes should not be left for government alone, non- governmental agencies and industries should support in the training and development of youth's in skill acquisition.
5. Government should ensure that infrastructural facilities are adequate and in good condition for instructional delivery.
6. Federal and state government should strengthen partnership and stakeholders' involvement in TVET in order to enhance education funding, apprenticeship, on- the- job training and industry involvement in curriculum development.

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